

Tensions and Harmonies in Research Paradigms and Research Methodology

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ABSTRACT

A practical problem arises when students simply mimic the research methodology, research paradigm, and the statistical analysis that their advisers used, for which reason they produce no new knowledge, considering that they only mechanically conduct research the way their advisers did. A methodological problem arises when researchers blindly utilize a paradigm that they mismatch with the methodology. Both problems result in an endless loop of methodological stagnation. The objectives of this article are to discuss both the tensions as well as harmonies between research paradigms and research methodologies with a view to ensuring research validity and reliability. This article is a qualitative critical integrative survey of the literature on research methodology and research paradigms. It explained which methodologies are incompatible and compatible with the four major research paradigms of behavioral science, interactionism, critical theory, and transformative paradigm, with case study illustrations. Instead of lazily instructing student researchers to merely follow their lead based upon their own research preferences and past practices, advisers must give room to their advisees to grow, be creative, critical, and explore different paradigms and methodologies in the conduct of their research. Only then can there be a shift that leads to progress in the construction of new knowledge.

Keywords: Reliability, Research Approach, Research Methodology, Research Paradigms, Validity

Introduction

Background of the Problem

Researchers either wittingly or unwittingly carry with them a built-in worldview or paradigm when they conduct research. However, many researchers, if not most, are unaware of the paradigm that is embedded in their research work. Worse, many more students and researchers have not been exposed to the concept of paradigms and do not even know what paradigm is.

Problem Statement

Based on the foregoing, two major problems arise. The first is the empirical or practical problem. The second is the methodological problem. Firstly, as far as practical problems are concerned, many student researchers merely imitate their professors by using the same old theories, the same research methodology, the same data collection methods, and the same statistical data analysis that their professors and advisers used in their research. The theories, methodology, and methods their professors employ are all good, but student researchers risk staying affixed in this pedagogical and methodological prison. Thus, these student researchers do not produce new knowledge, as they only mechanically conduct research the way their professors did.

Secondly, in terms of methodological problems, from many to most student researchers blindly conduct research without consideration to the foundational paradigm, due to which the research methodology they use might mismatch with the underlying research paradigm. Both empirical problems and methodological problems result in an endless loop of research and methodological stagnation. Student researchers end up as mere imitators and impersonators with no intellectual growth. They will forever be known as students of their former professors with their identities forever attached together.

In the first place, many researchers do not know what paradigms are. They are not aware that paradigms are related to research methodology, research designs, and statistical choices. This is the tragedy of paradigmatic unfamiliarity.

Research Gap

On the one hand, most articles and books on research discuss methodology in isolation with an unspoken dominant paradigm. On the other hand, most articles and books also discuss paradigms in isolation and not in connection to research methodologies. Many researchers treat the notions of methodology and paradigms as two isolates. See Figure 1 below.

Figure 1: Venn Diagram of the Separation between Methodology and Paradigm

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Rationale of the Study

There is a need for student researchers to learn about research paradigms, after which they will realize that paradigms affect and determine the methodology of a research endeavor. Subsequently, they can understand the way in which research paradigms impinge on their work. See Figure 2 below.

Figure 2: Paradigm Affects and Determines Methodology

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General Purpose

The general purpose of this article is to expose the readers, researchers, and especially student researchers, to the concept of paradigms and how they related to and affect research methodology. Doing so empowers researchers to ensure that their research work has validity or accuracy and reliability or consistency.

Specific Research Objectives

There are two specific research objectives of this article:

1. To discuss harmonies between research paradigms and research methodology; and,
2. To cite common cases of tensions or disharmonies between research paradigms and research methodologies which must be avoided.

Research Questions

The following are the two research questions of this article.

1. In what ways are research paradigms and research methodologies in harmony?
2. In what ways are research paradigms and research methodologies in tension or disharmony?

Significance of Study

Cognizant of research paradigms, researchers become aware of, understand, and utilize the correct elements of methodology for their research work, including research design, research data collection methods, and statistical data analysis.

Coverage of the Study

The scope of coverage of this article is the field of social sciences and education. The limitations of the findings of this article are in qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods research. The delimitation of the findings here relates to not directly focusing on humanities papers on the one hand and on natural science research work on the other hand.

Literature Review

Overview

The literature review of this article covers three themes. The first theme is research methodology. The second theme is research paradigm. The third theme is Japanese apprenticeship as a metaphor.

Research Methodology

The first theme is research methodology. In the widest sense, research methodology refers to the systematic approach to conduct research. It focuses on technical aspects and step-by-step procedures. These include research data collection methods, data analysis, and data interpretation. Research methodology provides a framework with which to assemble the research work. A well-written methodology makes sure that the qualitative findings and quantitative results of the research have credibility. With the step-by-step procedure laid down, the research is replicable, and other researchers can repeat the research to confirm its validity and reliability, if needed.

A more detailed general outline of the research methodology section of a research output contains the following information: research design (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2018), methodological choice (Saunders et al., 2023), time horizon, population and sample, sampling design, data collection methods (Babbie & Roberts, 2018), data collection instruments, data collection techniques and procedures, pilot testing, data analysis (Saunders et al., 2023), quantitative validity or qualitative accuracy, quantitative reliability or qualitative accuracy, triangulation, and research ethics (Denzin, 2007).

Research Paradigms

The next theme is research paradigm. In the philosophy of science, a paradigm in general is a worldview that guides how knowledge is studied and understood (Kuhn, 2012). A paradigm shift is a change in the assumptions and worldviews (Kuhn, 2012). Paradigms assume that knowledge, concepts, and theories are not absolutes, not permanent, and in fact always changing. Improvements in knowledge are not based on slow or gradual evolutionary changes. Rather, improvements by leaps and bounds in science are due to epistemological ruptures, such as from Newtonian physics to quantum physics.

In addition, there is a concept of falsifiability in science, according to which the purpose of scientific inquiry is not confirmation bias or to prove that we are correct. Rather, scientific research is more rigorous if we could falsify our findings to usher in a newer understanding of a given matter or phenomenon (Popper, 2002).

Thirdly, the concepts of paradigm shifts (Kuhn, 2012) and falsifiability (Popper, 2002) are integrated to provide a synthesis for the methodology of scientific research programs (MSRP) (Lakatos, 1968). While a hard core of scientific knowledge is solidly in place, there are peripheral hypotheses that can be confirmed or failed to be accepted, leading to either accepting the current state of knowledge or a break or a paradigm shift that leads to the production of new knowledge.

The philosophy of science involving paradigm shifts (Kuhn, 2012), falsification (Popper, 2002), and the methodology of scientific research programs (Lakatos, 1968) have direct impact and

application on the understanding of research paradigms. For one, the unwritten but hegemonic research paradigm is structural equilibrium, of which authors hardly mention when they conduct and publish their research work. For another, based on epistemic breaks (Kuhn, 2012) and falsifiability (Popper, 2002), there are research paradigms other than structural equilibrium.

The four major sets of research paradigms are the following: the dominant structural equilibrium on the one hand and the alternative research paradigms of interpretivism, critical theory, and dialectical structural transformation. See Table 1 below.

Table 1: Research Paradigms

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Change			
Subjective Agency	3 Critical Theory	4 Dialectical Structural Transformation	Objective Structures
	2 Interpretivism	1 Structural Functionalism	
Status Quo			

Based on the above table, there are four major sets of paradigms, corresponding to which are therefore four different worldviews in the conduct of research. Two paradigms are objective: namely, structural functionalism of paradigm one and dialectical radical structural transformation of paradigm four. The two remaining paradigms are subjective: namely, consciousness and interpretivism of paradigm two and critical theory of paradigm three. Two paradigms stay on the realm of the status quo: structural functionalism of paradigm one and consciousness and interpretivism of paradigm two. The two remaining paradigms promote change: critical theory of paradigm three promotes reformatory change, while dialectical radical structural transformation of paradigm four advances revolutionary change.

Japanese Apprenticeship

The last theme is Japanese notion of apprenticeship. Here, I use this concept as a metaphor to understand the state of the scholarly practice of research in the academic and publication world. In Japan, an apprentice (Deshi; 弟子) (Tadayuki, 2025) goes through three major stages. Collectively, they are Shuhari (守破離) (Sugiyama, 2025).

Stage one is Shu, during which the apprentice obeys the master and in the case of research, the principal investigator who is the professor of the student researchers. The role of the student apprentice is to learn from the expert, to guard or protect the ways in which the principal investigator conducts, analyzes, organizes, presents, and publishes the research. In general, there is no room for independent and critical thinking here. The aim is to learn from the best and to become copycats of the best.

Stage two is Ha, during which the apprentice breaks free from the master. The apprentice detaches from the master. The apprentice starts to produce work that digresses from the work of the master.

Stage three is Ri, during which the apprentice departs completely from the master. The apprentice leaves the comfort of doing things the way the master does things. The apprentice leaves the way the master taught and demonstrated the way things are done. The apprentice goes beyond the instructions of the master. See Table 2 below.

Table 2: Japanese Apprenticeship as a Metaphor

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Stages	Japanese Terms	Position	Function	Years
Stage 1	Shu (守)	Deshi (弟子)	To obey the master	5-10 years
Stage 2	Ha (破)	Independent Practice	To break from the master	10-20 years
Stage 3	Ri (離)	Shihan (Master) 師 (Teacher) 範 (Model, Exemplar)	To create one's own style	Lifetime

The challenge in research is that the majority of student researchers remain at stage 1 as “forever apprentice,” as they use the same old theories, the same research methodology, the same research data collection method, the same data analysis method that their professors and advisers use. Few student researchers break out from their professors and advisers to conduct research in novel ways. Rare are student researchers who become their own new masters.

Examples of students who became equal to or excel their professors include the following: The idealist Plato (Plato, 2007) was the teacher of the materialist Aristotle (Aristotle, 2009). While Plato taught Aristotle, Aristotle ended up developing a totally new school of thought in philosophy, thereby demonstrating his ability to leave the idealist mold of his teacher and create his own materialist brand of philosophy. Both Plato and Aristotle are equal giants in the realm of philosophy.

Another example is the relationship between Rawls (Rawls, 2009) and Sen (Sen, 2011). Both Rawls and Sen taught at Harvard University. Many students of economics, philosophy, political science, and sociology have read the idealist writings of Rawls on justice as fairness under transcendental institutionalism. The materialist Sen not only has read the writings of Rawls but also engaged in dialogue and debate with Rawls. Surpassing the modern-day guru of justice Rawls, Sen wrote a seminal work on justice by producing a materialist conception of justice based on real-life injustices. Not only that, Sen won the Nobel Prize in economics based on his research work on justice, which is a hallmark of an original dialectical thinker. See Figure below.

Figure 3: Later Thinker Sen Surpassed the Seminal Writer Rawls on Justice
Source: ©2025 Rey Ty

Gaps

There are three gaps in literature: one in methodology, another in paradigm, and the last one in the apprenticeship path.

First, in most research outputs, the gap in research methodology is reflexivity. Most researchers do not lay down their reflexivity, by which is meant to clarify their bias in their research. Like it or not, researchers have presuppositions about the phenomenon they investigate and what they want to achieve (“Reflexivity and Positionality in Research,” 2025). The personal points of view of authors may impinge on the writing and shaping of the direction and outcome of the research. Paradigms come in handy. Reflexivity is tied with research paradigms directly, as both expressly reveal one’s biases embedded in research (Berger, 2015; Finlay & Gough, 2003; Martin & Dandekar, 2022).

Second, the elephant in the room in research in general is the research paradigm. Most researchers do not, or never, reflect on the paradigm that undergirds their research work. Few discuss paradigms in their research. Fewer know what paradigms are. You can count on your fingers the number of researchers who employ and match a research paradigm with the research methodology they use.

Third, almost all student researchers end up as impersonators of their first-generation professors and advisers in terms of their research work. Reasons include convenience, safe zone, laziness, or lack of creative and critical thinking. This is what the academia calls academic inbreeding. No progress is achieved in the realm of research, as the second-generation student researchers who become the new professors and researchers recycle the same old theories and methodologies and worse they passed on to the third generation of student researchers. See Figure below.

Figure 4: No Progress in Regurgitating Old Theories and Methodology

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Methodology

Overview

This section provides details about the research methodology utilized in the preparation of this article. The purpose of this paper was to clarify the importance of the explicit use of research paradigms in the research process. This work employs the critical paradigm to reveal the importance of the explicit divulgence and utilization of which type of research paradigm for transparency and public disclosure, as each paradigm has an implicit perspective.

Type of Research

This article is a qualitative conceptual narrative survey of literature that provides a comprehensive discussion that reveals the relationship between paradigms and methodology. Specifically, it is a critical integrative literature review that provides an analysis, critique, and synthesis of the materials on paradigms and methodology, providing a meta-synthesis and a research agenda to fill the gap with a view to produce new insights (Torraco, 2005, 2016).

Research Design

This is a qualitative desk study. The inclusion documents in this qualitative research is literature related to research methodology and paradigms (Blackler & Brown, 1983; Bunniss & Kelly, 2010; Carey, 2021; Ty, 2023a; Weaver & Olson, 2006). Key textbooks and academic materials were selected from which data collection transpired (Adams et al., 2007; Archibald et al., 2019; Bailey, 2014; Barbour, 2019; Braun & Clarke, 2013; Brown, 2021).

Qualitative Data Thematic Analysis

For data analysis, after reading the literature on paradigms and research methodology, I generated initial codes, which are descriptions to commence organizing the data into groups. Thereafter, I sort my codes into themes at the thematic analysis stage, collating the codes into broader themes. Next, I defined and named the themes which led to the production of the narrative essay as well as original tables and figures. To ensure validity or accuracy and reliability or consistency, I utilized several sources for data triangulation.

Findings

This section has two subsections: the research findings or data analysis and the discussion subsection or the data interpretation.

Data Analysis

Harmonies between Paradigms and Methodology

Overall, there are four major research paradigms, namely: 1) Structural Equilibrium, 2) Consciousness and Interpretivism, 3) Critical Theory, and 4) Dialectical Radical Structural Transformation, with symbolic varying degrees of usage. See Figure below.

Figure 5: From Most Used to Least Used Research Paradigms
 Source: ©2025 Rey Ty

Paradigm one (structural equilibrium) and paradigm four (structural transformation) focus on and are best employed at the macro level. Paradigm three (interpretivism) is best fit for micro or individual analysis. Paradigm three (critical theory) is best utilized for meso or group level analysis. See Figure below.

Figure 6: Paradigms and the Different Levels of Analysis

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Paradigm One. The first paradigm is structural equilibrium. The common denominators of this paradigm are the following. In general, this paradigm is the best fit for macro level analysis. It searches for objective facts. Figures are important. Researchers quantify variables and seek measurable results. At the end of the day, this paradigm rests on the realm of the status quo. Changes are possible only as far as adjustments are concerned. Researchers using paradigm one work within the existing political economy.

Among the variants of paradigm one are the following:

1. Behavioral science
2. Functionalism
3. Positivism
4. Pragmatism
5. Structural Functionalism
6. Structuralism

Behavioral science is the scientific examination of observable behavior of human beings, including cultural, emotional, political, and social influences, through experiments (Chicago Booth, 2025). It aims to determine, depict, and clarify behavioral as well as social phenomena based on the standard practices of the scientific method (Gerstein et al., 2010). Functionalism is a theoretical framework commonly used in different social sciences, including political science and sociology, according to which institutional setups in society serve basic functions for the purpose of maintaining economic and political stability and social cohesion (Parsons & Smelser, 2012). Positivism is the epistemology according to which empirical observation of phenomena as well as logical and quantitative methods are essential to the acquisition of knowledge, to the exclusion of metaphysics (Strauss et al., 2018). Pragmatism is the belief and practice according to which theoretical propositions are acceptable on the basis of practical use and problem-solving impact (James, 1907; Peirce, 1878). Structural functionalism is the merger of the structural theory and the functional theory according to which society and organizations are whole entities composed of parts that function harmoniously in order to advance stability and unity (Merton, 1968). Structuralism is the theory according to which underlying structures

of society, such as fundamental cultural or linguistic foundations shape our human experiences and meaning-making (Lévi-Strauss, 2009; Rico & Halevy-Kirtchuk, 2018).

Authors can ensure the harmonious relationship between paradigm one and methodology in the following manners. The best fit methodology for use for the variants of structural equilibrium in paradigm one include quantitative methods, controlled experiments, close-ended structured surveys, as well as randomized statistics (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). Positivist methodology, deduction, experiments, as well as both cross-sectional and longitudinal time horizon fit well for use in paradigm 1 (Saunders et al., 2023).

Paradigm One aims to provide a detached, impartial, neutral, unbiased, objective, and quantifiable description of social reality. Through hypothetico-deductive testing, its end in view is the discovery of general laws of nature and of society. For this reason, paradigm one is most commonly used in natural, behavioral, and social sciences (Babbie & Roberts, 2018; Brown, 2021, 2021; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2018; Gerstein et al., 2010).

Paradigm Two. The second paradigm is interpretivism. Its common characteristics are the following. Researchers can best use paradigm two at the micro level. Its hallmark is the investigation of subjectivity. Researchers must bracket or set aside their prior knowledge and judgment when they describe lived experiences and engage in meaning-making (Husserl, 1984). They are engaged in describing human agency (Sartre, 2021) and providing thick description (Geertz, 1973).

Among the variants of paradigm two are the following:

1. Ethnography
2. Existentialism
3. Hermeneutics
4. Interpretivism
5. Phenomenology
6. Symbolic Interactionism

Ethnography involves the in-depth study, exposure to, participant observation of, and immersion of the researcher in the social reality and cultural observances of a given group or community (Geertz, 1973). Existentialism is the examination of individual existence, freedom, human agency, and meaning making (Beauvoir, 2017; Camus, 2018; Sartre, 2020, 2021). Hermeneutics focuses on the interpretation of the written word, as well as of human experiences in order to find out deeper meanings (Gadamer, 2008). Interpretivism is research that seeks to understand social phenomena based on the subjective meanings that people assign in their situation (Bevir & Rhodes, 2016). Phenomenology is the investigation of lived experiences from the viewpoint of an individual with the view to divulge the essence of a phenomenon (Heidegger, 2008; Husserl, 1984). Symbolic interactionism is the study of the manner in which social beings construct and interpret symbolic meaning via their interactions in society (Blumer, 1986).

Researchers can guarantee the harmonious connection between paradigm two and methodology in the following manners. The best-fit methodology for paradigm two are qualitative methods, inductive research, case studies, in-depth interviews, and ethnography (Saunders et al., 2023).

The key aim of paradigm two is to investigate the lived experiences of individuals, social interactions, and meaning making.

Paradigm Three. The third paradigm is critical theory. The common features of paradigm three are the following. Researchers can best use paradigm three at the meso level of analysis, such as investigating a group or a subgroup, such as women or an Indigenous community. For paradigm three, context matters. Researchers conduct analysis of the balance of political power among different participants in society. They dissect hegemony in society and engage in the production of a counter-hegemony through the use of human agency (Gramsci, 1989). Researchers using paradigm three are dissatisfied with the status quo and seek to reform it to deconstruct knowledge (Derrida, 2018, 2019) and to change power relations with a view to empower the marginalized groups (Foucault, 1980). However, they still work within the system.

Paradigm three critiques and call out racism, corruption, sexism, heteronormativity, and all types of injustices but not struggle against the root causes of injustice. The researchers of paradigm three are woke and aware of oppression. They are beholden to identity politics, culture wars, the ballot box, elections, and liberal reform. In short, they ask for justice within the unjust system but not transcend it.

Among the variants of paradigm three are the following:

1. Critical theory
2. Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion (DEI)
3. Feminism
4. Gender Studies
5. Intersectionality
6. Postmodernism
7. Poststructuralism
8. Queer Studies

Critical theory investigates the role of culture and critiques the structure of power in society and calls for social emancipation, social change, and social liberation (Habermas, 1990; Marcuse, 2007; Rockhill, 2017; E. Said, 2002; E. W. Said, 1994). Diversity, equity, and inclusion (DEI) is a call for fairness and representation of the marginalized people and groups (Beverly et al., 2025; Fagun, 2025). Feminism is the analysis of unequal gender relations and the advocacy for social justice and the rights of women (Hooks, 2014; Tong, 2024). Gender studies relate to the exploration of gender identity, relationships, and social construction. Intersectionality is the examination of the overlapping oppressive relations involving gender, race, and class (Crenshaw, 1991, 2023; Davis, 1983). Opposed to modernist idea of objective truth and progressive development, postmodernism is skeptical towards grand narratives, permanent truths, and fixed meanings, stressing knowledge is fragmented and plural, with unstable meaning (Baudrillard, 2019; Jameson, 1995; Lyotard, 1993). Poststructuralism rejects the permanence of structures in language, culture, knowledge, and power, calling for the decentering of subjects, deconstructing meaning, and recognize the role of power in epistemic conceptualization (Barthes, 1967; Derrida, 2019; Foucault, 1980). Queer studies challenge normative binary gender sexuality (Hall et al., 2013).

Wokeness started as the vocabulary of Black people in the U.S. as they refer to their awareness of the economic, social, cultural, and political problems with which they are confronted (West, 2004, 2014, 2017; West & Buschendorf, 2014). The school-to-prison pipeline is a dark reality for Blacks in the U.S.A. (Alexander, 2020). Wokeness refers on the one hand to the denunciation of injustice and on the other hand to the struggle for justice, civil rights, and full participation of all citizens in the democratic exercise. Paradigm three encourages people to be curious, study society, and engage in political participation for the empowerment of the hitherto marginalized. However, the far right uses the term pejoratively. They call out racism, sexism, corruption, oppression, and all forms of injustice and work within the system. They call for multiculturalism, inclusion, equity, and diversity.

Researchers can ensure harmonious connection between paradigm three and methodology in the following ways. The best fit methodology for paradigm three includes qualitative research design, discourse analysis, and narrative analysis (Creswell, 2007). The aim of paradigm three includes challenging hegemonic power structures, constructing counter-hegemonic power structures that gives room to the marginalized groups, and centering the importance of social justice.

Paradigm Four. The fourth paradigm is structural transformation. The common characteristics of paradigm four are the following. Similar to structural equilibrium of paradigm one, structural transformation of paradigm four is best used at the macro level of analysis. Analogous to paradigm one, paradigm four rests on the analysis of the whole structure. However, unlike paradigm one which works towards social equilibrium, paradigm four seeks to transform it. Paradigm four calls for liberation, not reform: that is the key difference between paradigm three (liberal reform) and paradigm four (radical liberation). With political economy (Balaam & Dillman, 2019; Marx, 1859; Ty, 2016, 2020, 2023b) as the overall worldview, paradigm four acknowledges that the economy determines politics and culture. In turn, politics and culture affect the economy. Changes at the structural level take place.

Some variants of paradigm four are the following:

1. Community Organizing
2. Dialectical Historical Materialism
3. Radical change
4. Structural transformation

Community organizing is the effort of identifying problems, building power, and bringing about empowerment and social transformation in the community (Alinsky, 2010). Dialectical historical materialism is the Marxist analysis of contradictions and class struggle that lead to the transformation of society (Borodulina, 1972). Radical change paradigm is advocacy for fundamental transformation of society.

Researchers can ensure harmonious relations between paradigm four and methodology in the following ways. The best fit methodology for paradigm four includes inductive research, action research (Ty, 2009, 2021a, 2021b, 2023c), and longitudinal time horizon, as researchers have to review the historical experiences, current problems, and plans for social change.

Tensions between Paradigms and Methodology

Ignorance of Paradigms. A major problem arises when researchers are not even aware of what paradigm impinges on their research. Worse, many researchers do not even know what paradigms are. For these reasons, researchers could unwittingly use methodology not suited for their research papers.

Paradigm-Methodology Mismatch. Here are some examples of major errors in combining the wrong paradigm with the wrong methodology. Take, for example, one, the combination of the positivist paradigm and the phenomenological methodology is disharmonious. This combination is incorrect for some reasons. First, the ontologies of positivism and phenomenology are incompatible, as the former searches for objective facts while the latter seeks subjective meanings. It is like mixing water with oil, which will not mix. In addition, the positivist paradigm utilizes statistics and figures, whereas the phenomenological methodology is comfortable only with subjective meaning making and interpretations.

Two, another mismatch is the use of the interpretivist paradigm with the methodology of randomized control trials (RCTs). For one, interpretivism requires understanding of context and phenomena as they are, which is qualitative, while randomized control trials require quantification as well as controlling and testing variables. The interpretivist paradigm is incompatible with the RCT methodology. For another, interpretivism relies on the investigation and subjective interpretation of lived experiences, while RCTs focus on objective and measurable independent, dependent, and other variables, not subjective interpretation.

Three, the critical theory paradigm is not at all aligned with the methodology that uses objective and nonpartisan survey questionnaires. For example, if a researcher is investigating the role of women, religious minorities, and ethnic minorities in advancing their rights in society, neutral surveys are the worst research instruments. When using critical race theory, critical legal theory, and feminist theory, researchers must ask the positionality of their research participants, their modes of their preferences in policy reforms. Hence, interviews are important for the critical theory paradigm. Using the close ended Likert scale survey questionnaire yield dry and neutral results of “excellent, very good, good, somewhat good, and not good.” Results from such close ended choices are useless for researchers who want to discover the subjective thinking, feelings, hopes, and fears of women, religious minorities, and ethnic minorities.

Four, pairing structural transformative paradigm with survey methodology using cross-sectional time horizon is erroneous and mismatched. Radical structural disequilibrium aims to radically change the foundations of society. Hence, the correct methodology must consider changes over time. Thus, using cross-sectional surveys is wrong, as it only provides a snapshot of social reality in one given period. The appropriate time horizon is longitudinal, not cross-sectional.

Take for example the social investigation of labor. We cannot investigate the situation of the working class in one snapshot in time only. The study of labor union spans at least three periods in time. The first period is the time during which child labor, unsafe working conditions, long working hours, and low wages were a reality. The second period is the time during which workers unionize, get politicized, and struggle for humane and just working conditions. The third period is the time during which workers have living wages, work eight hours maximum a day and six days a week, no child labor, paid holidays and vacation, and the like. But researchers

can extend the timeframe to include either progress or regression in the working conditions of the working class.

Five, the constructivist paradigm and hypothetico-deductive methodology are a wrong pair. Constructivism of paradigm two relies on the information that will emerge from qualitative interviews, lived experiences, or participant observation without any prejudgments. However, methodology that relies on a deductive hypothesis assumes that there is a relationship between variables, which the results of the quantitative research will either confirm or reject. Constructivism will yield a grounded theory, while a deductive methodology will confirm or reject a hypothesis. Hence, the premises of constructivism and deduction are different.

Six, postmodernist paradigm does not sit well with the methodology that relies on fixed coding. When researchers conduct postmodern interviews, they seek to find out new phenomena, new ways of thinking, new ways of being, and new descriptions. Researchers are yet to unearth these new discoveries. Thus, they will make a mistake if they use predetermined codes for their research. Researchers must reject fixed coding when conducting research that seeks to discover postmodern views.

Seven, the interpretivist paradigm does not go with generalized statistics. On the one hand, interpretivism values thick description and depth of understanding. On the other hand, statistics are concerned with generalizations. Thus, when studying the lived experiences of women, for example, researchers realize that developing generalizable representativeness of data about women in general is futile and mistaken. Statistics serve no meaningful function for interpretivist research, say, of an individual or a small community.

Eight, researchers learn in school that they must be detached when they conduct research. That is the mainstream and hegemonic perspective in all social science disciplines in the past. However, times have changed. New paradigms including qualitative research that involves values, gender relations, minorities, and racism do not align with the methodology that insists on the detached perspective. Hence, using a detached perspective in the conduct of critical theory research is erroneous. For example, when researchers engage in community organizing and community development, they embrace and adopt the community causes, embedding in and not detached from the demands and needs of the community members.

Discussion

Linking Back to Literature

In this section, I discuss the findings of the article in connection with the research questions. I relate, compare, and interpret the findings in relation to literature. As far as research question one is concerned, researchers must understand paradigms and align paradigms with the proper methodology. As far as research question two is concerned, researchers must be wary of employing methodologies that do not concur with the research paradigms.

Assumption

When the principal investigator (PI) of a funded research project hires graduate students as research assistants, the student researchers must of course assist the PI in the conduct of the research. As apprentices, these student researchers must learn to use the theories and methodologies laid down in the research grant proposal. To be sure, working under the

supervision of a seasoned principal investigator is an opportunity during which student researchers as apprentices can learn to conduct proper research. This is the learning phase only.

However, this is the beginning or the first step in the journey of a researcher, not the end stage. Researchers must grow and explore other paradigms and methodological options. Though student researchers must start as apprentices and learn from the best and from their professors and advisers, they need to eventually break free from the clutches of the same old theories, same old methodologies, and same old structural equilibrium paradigm. They must create their own style and become their own unique, critical, and creative researchers, rather than mere imitators of their professors.

Generalizations

Contrary to most research work that do not explicitly lay down their positionality in terms of stating the paradigm of the research and the reflexivity of the authors, this article stresses the importance of authors being cognizant of the paradigms they utilize in their research projects. This is the first step in ensuring the congruence of paradigms and methodologies in writing academic and research articles.

Contribution of the Findings

This article brings awareness to the importance of paradigms in the selection of methodology in research. The findings of this article contribute to the prevailing corpus of knowledge by calling authors to consciously consider the paradigms that guide their research.

Implications of the Findings

Understanding paradigms and selecting the proper paradigm of a specific research project ensures that the authors will use the proper research methodologies. Why is paradigm one most common. There are several reasons. Seniors pass it on to us. We use it mechanically and uncritically. We become intellectually lazy. We are contented with the status quo. We are happy to make minor tweaks with the status quo. The most common users of paradigm one are institutions, governments, all kinds of organizations, and bureaucracies, when they are balancing their budgets or profit seeking.

Why is paradigm two necessary? It is used to learn about the human agency of individuals, their thoughts, feelings, perceptions, hopes, fears, likes, and dislikes. Key variants of paradigm two include existentialism and phenomenology. Some prominent authors in this tradition include Sartre, the French existentialist (Sartre, 2020, 2021). Aside from anthropologists, who use paradigm two? Surprisingly, Harvard Business Review uses this constructivist paradigm, resorting to investigating exceptional case studies of unique situations, not generalizable statistics of metadata (Harvard Business Review, 2025).

Why is paradigm three necessary? Researchers use paradigm three to analyze power and inequality as well as question the dominant narrative. With paradigm three, researchers listen to and learn about the conditions as well as the demands of marginalized groups. They include women, Indigenous peoples, ethnic minorities, religious minorities, migrant workers, as well as climate and animal-rights activists. Here, researchers pursue social justice and equality. Paradigm three underpins the civil rights advocacy of Martin Luther King, Jr. (King & Washington, 2005) and Malala Yousafzai's advocacy for the education of the girl child and the rights of women (Yousafzai, 2025).

What is the use value of paradigm four? Paradigm four is a useful tool to analyze extreme crisis situations. It is the correct paradigm to utilize to study crisis management, climate crisis, armed conflict, civil war, and international wars. Why is it the least used paradigm. Clearly, it is most useful in crisis situations, which is rare, and that answers the reasons for which this paradigm is least used. There is risk in using this paradigm, as researchers could be considered as taking sides for social transformation and opposed to the status quo. Take for instance, writing about the Ukraine-Russia conflict, Israel-Palestine conflict, and the like. Researchers take a back seat in terms of speaking up or taking up a stand as doing so could be dangerous to one’s academic and professional career, as they could be subject to cancel culture. Readers might treat your research as taking one side over another, even if that is not the purpose of your study. Worse, readers might consider you as taking the opposing side.

Limitations

There are limitations that affect the utilization of research paradigms. Many researchers use only one paradigm throughout their whole academic professional career. For instance, the structural equilibrium paradigm, which is mostly unspoken, underpin most research projects, as it is the dominant research paradigm. Paradigm one serves as a research prison from which authors have difficulty breaking lose. Although not all, many academic institutions as well as research foundations assume that researchers use the often-unspoken paradigm of structural equilibrium. Hence, researchers might experience difficulties in working with paradigms other than paradigm one. Student researchers should be cognizant of this limitation when they attempt to employ paradigms two, three, or four.

Summary

See Figure below for the summary of the discussion on paradigm and methodology.

Figure 7: Summary of Implications of the Four Paradigms

Source: ©2025 Rey Ty

Conclusion

Summary of the Findings

Research question one reveals the correct combination of research paradigm and research methodology. There are four major types of paradigms, while research methodology includes qualitative and quantitative as well as the mixed-method methodology. With concrete examples, response to research question two warns about the misuse of the inappropriate combination of paradigm and methodology and calls for researchers to avoid them.

Concluding Remarks

Many student researchers stay affixed at the level of neophyte researchers, always only following the lead of their professors and advisers, signifying no further intellectual growth. They need to find their purpose as well as demonstrate independence, not merely staying in the realm of neophyte impersonators. First things first, all researchers must learn about paradigms and learn how to apply them in their research work.

Recommendations

Student researchers start as apprentices of their excellent faculty advisers and outstanding principal investigators who access research grants. During this time, they learn from the best on how to conduct research. However, after learning the ropes of conducting research, student researchers must grow, be creative, be critical, and explore different paradigms and methodologies in the conduct of their research. In that way, from apprentices, they become their own research masters who forge their own research paths that reflect their own positionality in the use of paradigms and methodologies. They could develop and employ local, Indigenous, or even new methodologies to match their paradigms or worldviews.

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